

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF PARALLEL CFD SIMULATION OF SHIP MOTION AT ADVERSE SEA CONDITIONS

Vyara KOLEVA-EFREMOVA, Todor GUROV*, Grigor NIKOLOV, Dobrin EFREMOV**

Abstract. *With the implementation of the Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) into the industry and science, it becomes possible to solve complex tasks such as hydrodynamics analysis, weather forecast, biological engineering and etc. Both, licensed and open source CFD products are available at the market but the most important question stays: "How to parallel the task to achieve better performance in a short time?". By increasing the complexity of the task, to respond to this question becomes more and more difficult.*

In this article we investigate a CFD simulation of a ship motion at waves using the OpenFoam software, the preparation of the fluid domain, boundary conditions and ship hull is done by specialists of BSHC. Such a complicate task requires a lot of computational resources. For this experiment the Avitohol HPC platform is used to achieve the performance ratio of different cases. The MPI interface is used for paralleling the CFD model between the cluster's nodes. The results are compared with the CFD simulation performance of the ship motion at calm water and are made conclusions about the behaviour and efficient of Avitohol's resources. Also is made plans and schedule for the future project of BSHC for CFD computational cluster.

Key words: *CFD, MPI, OpenFoam, Parallel simulations, Ship.*

INTRODUCTION

A simulation of multiphase flow requires great computational resources. This is mostly the main limitation when we speak about CFD simulations. The Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) is used to solve complex problems that involve fluid flows based on numerical analysis and data structures [1, 12]. The precision of these numerical methods depends on the mesh refinement. In fact more elements/cells mean higher accuracy, but lead to higher memory consumption and core hours for number processing. One solution is to use some HPC cluster to run such complex simulations which are not suitable for a desktop, or we can reduce the costs associated with computational resources by using suitable cloud-based solutions like SimScale [2]. Such kind of research could lead to optimization of the assembling of "supercomputers", for example about the future project of BSHC for CFD computational cluster.

For this experiment, the Avitohol supercomputer system is used [3]. It consists of 150 computational servers HP SL250s Gen8, equipped with two Intel Xeon E5-2650v2 CPUs and two Intel Xeon Phi 7120P co-processors, 64GB RAM, two 500GB hard drives, interconnected with non-blocking FDR InfiniBand running at 56Gbp/s line speed. The total number of cores is 20700 and the total RAM is 9600 GB, respectively.

The CFD test cases consider the ship motion at calm water and waves respectively. Till now the first one is often described, while the second is not still widely studied due to insufficient computer and software capacity.

As a CFD solver it is selected OpenFOAM v5.0. Compared to the others CFD solvers, available on the market like ANSYS Fluent for example, OpenFOAM has significant advantages - it is free, open source solution with high reliability and accuracy. It is easy scriptable and allows effective optimisation by rapidly changing the setted up geometry. One of the experts in the CFD industry - TotalSIM chooses OpenFOAM for their solutions [4]. Version 5.0 is backward compatibility but includes also new functionalities compared to version 4.0, like waves modelling, which is needed for the intent of our study [5]. To run our job on parallel the Message Passing

Interface (MPI) will be used between the cluster's SMP nodes. The Avitohol has available Intel MPI library version 2.2.

*Institute for Information and Communication Technologies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences Acad. G. Bonchev str., Block 25A, Sofia 1113, Bulgaria

**Bulgarian Ship Hydrodynamics Centre (BSHC-BAS), Varna, Bulgaria Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS)

The aim of this experiment is to find dependencies between the parallel efficiency achieved in case of a ship at calm water and this one achieved in case of the same ship in multiphase flow. With this we can made conclusions about the Avitohol’s potential.

PRE-PROCESSING

Mathematical approach

Computational Hydrodynamics is an analysis using different mathematics methods to solve some differential equations such as the Navier-Stokes unit. Because their analytical solution is possible (for now), only in some particular cases, it is necessary to use numerical approaches to solve it. The method used to solve the mentioned equations, implemented in the academic software applications, is the finite volume method. In this case, the computational domain defined by the set boundary conditions of the partial differential equations is divided into a finite number of elements called a mesh. The number of cells in typical computing mesh can reach tens of millions, and even then the mesh resolution may not be sufficient to accurately estimate the magnitudes of studied fluid flow. The artificially use of a large number of network cells, results in an indefinite increasing of the work time required for numerical simulations. To overcome this disadvantage, one way is to apply parallel data processing.

Let spatial and temporal domains are defined by $\Theta_t \supset K^n$ and $(0, t)$ respectively, where K^n introduce the number of space dimension, with Ω_t we denote the boundary of Θ_t , x and t represent spatial and temporal coordinates. The Navier-Stokes equations for incompressible fluid flow are [13]:

$$(1) \quad \rho \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \cdot \nabla u - f \right) - \nabla \cdot \sigma = 0 \text{ for } (0, t)$$

$$(2) \quad \nabla \cdot u = 0 \text{ for } (0, t)$$

where

ρ, u, f and σ are density, velocity, body force and the stress tensor respectively.

The Dirichlet and Neumann-type boundary conditions are taken into account and are represented as follows:

$$(3) \quad u = g \text{ on } (\Omega_t)_g \quad n \cdot \sigma = h \text{ on } (\Omega_t)_h$$

where

$(\Omega_t)_g$ and $(\Omega_t)_h$ are subsets of the boundary Ω_t and n is normal vector. The initial condition of the velocity is defined on Θ_t at $t = 0$:

$$(4) \quad u(x, 0) = u_0 \quad \text{on} \quad \Theta_0$$

GEOMETRY AND TEST CONDITIONS

The selected geometry for this study is standard ship model KCS (KRISO Container Ship). The ship model geometry is consist by 116062 numbers of cells and converted to STL file format, which describes only the surface geometry of the three-dimensional object without any representation of colour, texture or other common CAD model attributes [6]. On figure 1 is shown the 3D model of the ship hull.

Fig. 1. 3D ship model

For the purpose of this study, the domain is divided to two fluid subsections - water and air [12]. The mesh is generated via Cervical Vertebral Maturation (CVM) method (fig.2),[7]. The total number of cells of the mesh is 1 154 737. One of the sides of the domain box is configured to be movable to generate the Boundary Conditions of the wave's pattern. OpenFOAM v5.0 includes libwaves.so library, which is required for the wave generation and will be loaded at run time.

Fig. 2. Mesh generation

In CFD, the strategy for increasing efficiency in the simulation process is to divide the main task into several sub-tasks [14]. In defining the acceleration coefficient of the computational process, the interaction between the times required to solve the problem of using a single computational point and the time to applying parallel processing:

$$(5) \quad L = T_s / T_p$$

where

T_s is the time for sequential processing and T_p is the time for parallel processing of the task.

The computational efficiency of the system is determined by the value of divided by the number of computer cores, ideally. One of the reasons for poor performance is a poorly balanced cluster. In order to predict the expected theoretical acceleration in parallel processing, the most popular approach is the Amdal model (L_A), which shows the maximum theoretical acceleration of the simulation:

$$(6) \quad L_A = NP + (1 - P)$$

where

N represents the computational physical nuclei P the number of parallel processes.

In a nutshell, Amdal's law shows that the effectiveness of parallel simulation depends on the algorithm of the task and is bounded by each task. Increasing concurrent processes is not effective for all tasks, even more if you take into account the data transmission time between the nodes, expression (6) has its maximum. This implies a limitation in the scalability of the computational scheme, which means that from a certain point the addition of more computational cores will increase the time required for the numerical simulation.

As a pre-processing, the mesh is decomposed, meaning the domain is grouped into pieces based on the used number of logical cores. For this action is used the scotch algorithm which requires no geometric input from the user and attempts to minimise the number of processor boundaries [8]. Other important controls are configured such as time control, time precision, data writing etc. Total time of the simulation is set to 10s, time step is 0.001, write interval - 1, write precision - 6 (default value).

OpenFOAM has several solvers applicable for different tasks. For this study, icoFoam solver is selected since it is used for incompressible, laminar flow of Newtonian fluids. The solver uses PISO algorithm to solve the continuity equation and moment equation. It is an efficient method to solve the Navier-Stokes equations in unsteady problems [9][10].

RESULTS

CFD results

At figure 3 it's shown the KCS ship into calm water (without waves). While at figures 4 and 5 we can see the wave pattern and how the waves interact with the ship's body. The CFD results are represented via ParaView visualization application - this is the post-processing tool provided by OpenFOAM. ParaView operates a tree-based structure in which data can be filtered from the top-level case module to create sets of sub-modules [11].

Fig. 3. CFD simulation of the wave pattern of a ship on calm water

Fig. 4. CFD simulation of the wave pattern of a ship on multiphase flow (1/2)

Fig. 5. CFD simulation of the wave pattern of a ship on multiphase flow (2/2)

OpenFOAM scaled results

In tables 1 and 2 are shown the scaled results by the simulations at calm water and at waves. In the pre-processing stage, the task was decomposed several times based on the number of used CPU cores. Since this decomposition is executed by the host machine (it is not run in parallel) the total time for the decomposition is not included to the final average time of the simulation because it is not take effect on it. As we already mentioned, the Avitohol system consist of 150 servers (nodes), integrated into 8 racks. Each node is equipped with two Intel Xeon E5-2650v2 CPUs with 16 CPU cores. Each rack has 20 nodes, so with decomposing the task from 16 to 1024 pieces we can test: the parallel efficiency between the nodes in one node, between the nodes and between the racks of Avitohol, and to make conclusions about the performance capabilities of the system.

The "Average time" column in the two tables is calculated based on the elapsed time of the simulation for 10 iterations. It is taken the clock time from the log of the simulation, since this is the "real" time required to complete the simulation.

Open Foam scaled results for the MPI parallel tests (CFD of a ship at calm water)

Table 1

Nodes	CPU Cores	Average Time(s) per 1000 steps	Speedup performance	Speedup, doubled number of nodes
1	16	2090	-	-
2	32	1392	1.50	0.00
4	64	1087	1.28	0.85
8	128	1213	0.90	0.70
16	256	2037	0.60	0.66
32	512	4543	0.45	0.75
64	1024	7123	0.64	1.42

Open Foam scaling results for the MPI parallel tests (CFD of a ship at waves)

Table 2

Nodes	Logical Cores	Average Time(s) per 175 steps	Speedup performance	Speedup, doubled number of nodes
1	16	3989	-	-
2	32	2541	1.57	0.00
4	64	2316	1.10	0.70
8	128	1570	1.48	1.34
16	256	4665	0.34	0.23
32	512	8310	0.56	1.67
64	1024	31370	0.26	0.47

CONCLUSIONS

At figures 6, 7 and 8 we can see the speedup and the parallel efficiency, achieved as a result from the Avitohol calculations. It is important to mark that the speedup depends from many components and it's different for both CFD cases (calm water and waves). Till the speedup decreases, the task permits to be decomposed to more and more pieces. From certain point (128 cores for calm water and 256 cores for multiphase flow), additional decomposition is unwanted, since this slows the calculations. We can conclude that the total number of used cores must be increased/doubled whit the complexity of the task. When doubling the used number of cores, the aim is to achieve execution time decreased by the factor of 1. 5. For both cases we can say, that the total parallel efficiency is close to the using of 256 cores of Avitohol system.

Fig. 6. Speedup

Fig. 7. Speedup (doubled number of cores)

Fig. 8. Parallel efficiency

In this work we presented parallel CFD simulations of a ship in different environment via OpenFoam CFD toolbox. The results from scalability of using MPI parallel model at calm water and adverse sea conditions like waves were studied based on the introduced scalability. The "Pre- processing" section describes the used mathematical approach and the configurations made via the OpenFOAM CFD tool. The "Results" section represents the CFD results of both test cases and the numerical results of the parallel jobs. The achieved performance results are visualised and analysed in section "Conclusions". As a future work, we plan to test the simulation models using Intel Xeon Phi coprocessors which are available in the Avitohol supercomputer system and by this investigation is made plans and schedule for the future project of BSHC for CFD computational cluster.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to thank to Bulgarian Ship Hydrodynamic Center - Varna (BSHC), for their support, as well as Dr. Grigor Nikolov for his valuable advices and guidance. This work was supported by the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science under the National Research Program “Young scientists and postdoctoral students” approved by DCM # 577 / 17.08.2018.

REFERENCES

- [1] Computational fluid dynamics: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Computational_fluid_dynamics.
- [2] SimScale simulation platform: https://www.simscale.com/?utm_campaign=quora19_gg&utm_medium=social&utm_source=quora.
- [3] ACDC at ICT-BAS, <http://www.hpc.acad.bg/>.
- [4] TotalSIM chooses OpenFOAM: <https://www.totalsimulation.co.uk/why-openfoam/>.
- [5] OpenFOAM 5.0 release: <https://openfoam.org/release/5-0/>.
- [6] STL file format: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/STL_\(file_format\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/STL_(file_format)).
- [7] CVM method: Juha Kortelainen, "Meshing Tools for Open Source CFD - A Practical Point of View", Research report VTT-R-02440-09 (24), 2009, <https://www.vtt.fi/inf/julkaisut/muut/2009/VTT-R-02440-09.pdf>.
- [8] Scotch decomposition: <https://cfd.direct/openfoam/user-guide/v6-running-applications-parallel/>.
- [9] icoFoam solver: <https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/guides/latest/doc/guide-applications-solvers-incompressible-icoFoam.html>.
- [10] OpenFOAM solvers: <https://www.openfoam.com/documentation/user-guide/standard-solvers.php>.
- [11] ParaView: <https://cfd.direct/openfoam/user-guide/v6-paraview/>.
- [12] Efremov, D. V., Milanov, E. M.: Hydrodynamics of DARPA SUBOFF Submarine at Shallowly Immersion Conditions. TransNav, the International Journal on Marine Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation, Vol.13, No.2, <http://dx.doi.org/10.12716/1001.13.02.09>, pp. 337-342, 2019.
- [13] https://openfoamwiki.net/index.php/OpenFOAM_guide/The_SIMPLE_algorithm_in_OpenFOAM.
- [14] Sunderran, A. G., Ashworth, M., Li, N., Moulinec, C., Fournier, Y. Towards Petascale Computing With Parallel CFD Codes. Uribe STFC Daresbury Laboratory, Warrington, University of Manchester, UK.

**MARITIME TRANSPORTATION
AND PORT OPERATIONS**
